

The Efficacy of Neuromuscular Blocking Agents in ARDS**Tom Paruppallil Kurian¹, Sreeharsha B², Nithya Dinesh³, Muktabai⁴**¹Junior Consultant, Dept. Critical Care Medicine, Bhagwan Mahaveer Jain Hospital, Vasanthnagar, Bangalore²Junior Consultant, Dept. Anaesthesia and Critical Care, Cauvery Heart and Multispeciality Hospital, Mysore³Senior Resident, Dept. Anaesthesia and Critical Care, Indira Gandhi Hospital, Dwarka Delhi⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. Anesthesiology, Mahadevappa Rampure Medical College, Kalabauragi

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Abstract:

In patients undergoing mechanical ventilation for the acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), neuromuscular blocking agents may improve oxygenation and decrease ventilator-induced lung injury but may also cause muscle weakness. We evaluated clinical outcomes after 2 days of therapy with neuromuscular blocking agents in patients with early, severe ARDS.

Materials and Methods: In this multicenter, double-blind trial, 340 patients presenting to the intensive care unit (ICU) with an onset of severe ARDS within the previous 48 hours were randomly assigned to receive, for 48 hours, either cisatracurium besylate (178 patients) or placebo (162 patients). Severe ARDS was defined as a ratio of the partial pressure of arterial oxygen (PaO₂) to the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) of less than 150, with a positive end-expiratory pressure of 5 cm or more of water and a tidal volume of 6 to 8 ml per kilogram of predicted body weight.

Results: The hazard ratio for death at 90 days in the cisatracurium group, as compared with the placebo group, was 0.68 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.48 to 0.98; P= 0.04), after adjustment for both the baseline PaO₂:FiO₂ and plateau pressure and the Simplified Acute Physiology II score.

Conclusions: In patients with severe ARDS, early administration of a neuromuscular blocking agent improved the adjusted 90-day survival and increased the time off the ventilator without increasing muscle weakness.

Keywords: ARDS, cisatracurium.

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Introduction

(ARDS) is characterized by hypoxic respiratory failure; it affects both medical and surgical patients. [1] Despite rigorous physiological management, [2] in most studies, ARDS has been fatal in 40 to 60% of patients. [3-7] Neuromuscular blocking agents are used in a large but highly variable proportion of patients with ARDS. [8-12] Current guidelines indicate that neuromuscular blocking agents are appropriate for facilitating mechanical ventilation when sedation alone is inadequate, most notably in patients with severe gas-exchange impairments. [10] In a four-center randomized, controlled trial of gas exchange in 56 patients with ARDS, [13] infusion of a neuromuscular blocking agent for a period of 48 hours was associated with improved oxygenation and a trend toward lower mortality in the intensive care unit (ICU). However, this study was not designed or powered to evaluate mortality. Thus, the benefits and risks of adjunctive therapy with neuromuscular blocking agents in patients with ARDS who were receiving lung-protective mechanical ventilation [14] require further

evaluation. We conducted a multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind trial to determine whether a short period of treatment with the neuromuscular blocking agent cisatracurium besylate early in the course of severe ARDS would improve clinical outcomes.

Materials and Methods

In this multicenter, double-blind trial, 340 patients presenting to the intensive care unit (ICU) with an onset of severe ARDS within the previous 48 hours were randomly assigned to receive, for 48 hours, either cisatracurium besylate (178 patients) or placebo (162 patients). Severe ARDS was defined as a ratio of the partial pressure of arterial oxygen (PaO₂) to the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) of less than 150, with a positive end-expiratory pressure of 5 cm or more of water and a tidal volume of 6 to 8 ml per kilogram of predicted body weight

Results

We enrolled 340 patients, of whom 178 were randomly assigned to cisatracurium and 162 to placebo. We excluded 986 patients. One patient in the cisatracurium group withdrew consent before treatment was started, and data for this patient were therefore not included in the analysis. The median time from the diagnosis of ARDS to study inclusion was 16 hours (interquartile range, 6 to 29) in the study population and did not differ significantly between the cisatracurium group (median, 18 hours; interquartile range, 6 to 31) and the placebo group (median, 15 hours; interquartile range, 7 to 27; $P = 0.45$). The median time from initiation of mechanical ventilation to study inclusion did not differ significantly between the cisatracurium group (22 hours; interquartile range, 9 to 41) and the placebo group (21 hours; interquartile range, 10 to 42; $P=0.91$). The only significant difference between the two groups at baseline was a lower mean PaO₂:FIO₂ value in the cisatracurium group. The Cox regression model yielded a hazard ratio for death at 90 days in the cisatracurium group, as compared with the placebo group, of 0.68 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.48 to 0.98; $P=0.04$), after adjustment for the baseline PaO₂:FIO₂, SAPS II, and plateau pressure. The crude 90-day mortality was 31.6% (95% CI, 25.2 to 38.8) in the cisatracurium group and 40.7% (95% CI, 33.5 to 48.4) in the placebo group ($P = 0.08$). The beneficial effect of cisatracurium on the 90-day survival rate was confined to the two thirds of patients presenting with a PaO₂:FIO₂ ratio of less than 120. Among these patients, the 90-day mortality was 30.8% in the cisatracurium group and 44.6% in the control group. The absolute difference in 28-day mortality (mortality in the cisatracurium group minus mortality in the placebo group) was -9.6 percentage points

Discussion

Treatment with the neuromuscular blocking agent cisatracurium for 48 hours early in the course of severe ARDS improved the adjusted 90-day survival rate, increased the numbers of ventilator-free days and days outside the ICU, and decreased the incidence of barotrauma during the first 90 days. It did not significantly improve the overall 90-day mortality. Strengths of this trial include the methods used to minimize bias (blinded randomization assignments, a well-defined study protocol, complete follow-up, and intention-to-treat analyses). The recruitment of a large number of patients from 20 multidisciplinary ICUs where international standards of care are followed suggests that our data can be generalized to other ICUs. Limitations of the trial include the fact that our results were obtained for cisatracurium besylate and may not apply to other neuromuscular blocking agents. Furthermore, we did not assess the use of a neuromuscular blocking agent late in the

course of ARDS or use on the basis of plateau-pressure or transpulmonary-pressure measurements.¹⁶ Another limitation is the absence of data on conditions known to antagonize or potentiate neuromuscular blockade. However, any condition that increases the duration of neuromuscular blockade would have adversely affected the patients receiving the neuromuscular blocking agent. The mechanisms underlying the beneficial effect of neuromuscular blocking agents remain speculative. A brief period of paralysis early in the course of ARDS may facilitate lung-protective mechanical ventilation by improving patient-ventilator synchrony and allowing for the accurate adjustment of tidal volume and pressure levels, thereby limiting the risk of both asynchrony-related alveolar collapse and regional alveolar-pressure increases with overdistention. Another possible mechanism of the benefit involves a decrease in lung or systemic inflammation. [15] The main safety concern with the use of a neuromuscular blocking agent is muscle weakness; the risk varies among agents. [18,19] Steroidal compounds (vecuronium, pancuronium, and rocuronium) may carry the highest risk of myopathy,²⁰ although myopathy has also been reported with benzyloquinolines, including cisatracurium besylate. [21,22]

Conclusions

In patients with severe ARDS, early administration of a neuromuscular blocking agent improved the adjusted 90-day survival and increased the time off the ventilator without increasing muscle weakness

References

1. Ware LB, Matthay MA. The acute respiratory distress syndrome. *N Engl J Med* 2000;342:1334-49
2. Malhotra A. Low-tidal-volume ventilation in the acute respiratory distress syndrome. *N Engl J Med* 2007;357:1113-20
3. Bernard GR. Acute respiratory distress syndrome: a historical perspective. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2005; 172:798-806.
4. Brun-Buisson C, Minelli C, Bertolini G, et al. Epidemiology and outcome of acute lung injury in European intensive care units: results from the ALIVE study. *Intensive Care Med* 2004; 30:51-61.
5. Esteban A, Anzueto A, Frutos F, et al. Characteristics and outcomes in adult patients receiving mechanical ventilation: a 28-day international study. *JAMA* 2002; 287:345-55
6. Esteban A, Ferguson ND, Meade MO, et al. Evolution of mechanical ventilation in response to clinical research. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2008; 177:170-7.
7. Rubenfeld GD, Caldwell E, Peabody E, et al. Incidence and outcomes of acute lung injury. *N Engl J Med* 2005; 353:1685-93.

8. Hansen-Flaschen JH, Brazinsky S, Basile C, Lanken PN. Use of sedating drugs and neuromuscular blocking agents in patients requiring mechanical ventilation for respiratory failure: a national survey. *JAMA* 1991; 266:2870-5.
9. Mehta S, Burry L, Fischer S, et al. Canadian survey of the use of sedatives, analgesics, and neuromuscular blocking agents in critically ill patients. *Crit Care Med* 2006; 34:374-80.
10. Murray MJ, Cowen J, DeBlock H, et al. Clinical practice guidelines for sustained neuromuscular blockade in the adult critically ill patient. *Crit Care Med* 2002;30: 142-56.
11. Samuelson KA, Larsson S, Lundberg D, Fridlund B. Intensive care sedation of mechanically ventilated patients: a national Swedish survey. *Intensive Crit Care Nurs* 2003; 19:350-62.
12. Vender JS, Szokol JW, Murphy GS, Nit-sun M. Sedation, analgesia, and neuromuscular blockade in sepsis: an evidence-based review. *Crit Care Med* 2004;32: Suppl: S554-S561.
13. Gainnier M, Roch A, Forel JM, et al. Effect of neuromuscular blocking agents on gas exchange in patients presenting with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Crit Care Med* 2004;32:113-9
14. The Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome Network. Ventilation with lower tidal volumes as compared with traditional tidal volumes for acute lung injury and the acute respiratory distress syndrome
15. Forel JM, Roch A, Marin V, et al. Neuro-muscular blocking agents decrease inflammatory response in patients presenting with acute respiratory distress syndrome
16. Talmor D, Sarge T, Malhotra A, et al. Mechanical ventilation guided by esophageal pressure in acute lung injury. *N Engl J Med* 2008;359:2095-104
17. Segredo V, Caldwell JE, Matthay MA, Sharma ML, Gruenke LD, Miller RD. Persistent paralysis in critically ill patients after long-term administration of vecuronium. *N Engl J Med* 1992;327:524-8.
18. Murray MJ, Coursin DB, Scuderi PE, et al. Double-blind, randomized, multicenter study of doxacurium vs. pancuronium in intensive care unit patients who require neuromuscular blocking agents. *Crit Care Med* 1995; 23:450-8.
19. Testelmans D, Maes K, Wouters P, et al. Rocuronium exacerbates mechanical ventilation-induced diaphragm dysfunction in rats. *Crit Care Med* 2006; 34:3018- 23.
20. Davis NA, Rodgers JE, Gonzalez ER, Fowler AA III. Prolonged weakness after cisatracurium infusion: a case report. *Crit Care Med* 1998; 26:1290-2.
21. Leatherman JW, Fluegel WL, David WS, Davies SF, Iber C. Muscle weakness in mechanically ventilated patients with severe asthma. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 1996; 153:1686-90.